

MICROECONOMETRIC VALUATION ESTIMATES AND STRATEGY OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS

Abstract:

Entrepreneurship action does not often apply techniques available to identify underlying attributes of processes and adequately analyze the strategy to be adopted for the establishment and amelioration of a particular business. Hence, the objective of this paper is threefold: to present the hedonic prices technique; discuss the utilities of the hedonic method; estimate a model of hedonic prices for the real estate sector of the Great Metropolitan Area of Sao Paulo (RMSP) and identify the attributes that in fact values and devalues residential property. The results bring clarifying information for economic and strategic valuation of investment projects.

Keywords: Economic Valuation; Hedonic Prices; Entrepreneurship.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The hedonic pricing models are those which take into account the characteristics of goods for explaining its prices. They have their origin back in the twentieth century, precisely at the end of the 30s. Before the development of specific theories related to the subject, Andrew T. Court (1939) was the pioneer in this type of analysis, when GM funded activities aiming to prevent the U.S. government to control prices applied by the company in order to stabilize production levels and unemployment.

Contradicting the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), whereby the price index of the GM brand had risen 45% in the 1925-1935 period, Court (1939) used a single equation procedure - corresponding to the first stage of the proposed model by Rosen (1974) - which allows the analysis of how each feature influences the final price of the vehicle, concluding that, in fact, the prices of GM-branded cars had fallen 55% in that period.

Court's (1939) procedure was then called the hedonic price method, based on utilitarian philosophy that promoted the hedonist thought based on the pursuit of pleasure, defining comparisons of hedonic prices as "those which recognize the potential contribution of any good - a car motor, for instance - for the welfare and happiness they can provide for their customers".

The theory of hedonic prices, attributed to the authors Lancaster (1966) and Rosen (1974), takes into account various attributes of a good in the process of price formation. Although the empirical application of hedonic pricing models already occurred earlier, the models lacked a well defined theoretical support. According to Sartoris (1996), the empirical applications are popular in the works of Griliches (1961), which inspired many other empirical works in different markets, for both durable and non-durable goods such as cars and morning cereal.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Technical Review of Literature

Following the work by Rosen (1974), the theory of hedonic prices at any location on a surface is represented by a vector of coordinates $z = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k)$, in which z represents the property in question and k , the different features contained in a good.

The function that relates the price of the acquired good and its characteristics is expressed by $p = f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k)$. Thus, $p(z)$ is the set of hedonic prices that guide locational decisions of consumers and producers for bundles of different characteristics of the product bought and sold.

The function that relates the price of the acquired good is expressed by $p = f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k)$. Therefore, $p(z)$ is the set of hedonic prices that guide the decisions of consumers and producers in relation to different bundles of product characteristics bought and sold.

A linear model of hedonic prices can be expressed as follows:

$$p = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k z_k \quad (1)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z_k} = \beta_k$$

Thus, p represents the price of a good; z_k represents a bundle of characteristics of this good x ; and β_k represents the implicit or marginal value of the k -th feature of the good in question, showing how the price p of a good varies as this is, *ceteris paribus*, endowed with an additional amount of z_k attributes.

A work that applies the theory of hedonic prices is that of Murray and Sarantis (1999). The authors examine the price-quality cars in the UK, in which the main goal was to employ a more comprehensive set of data on the work of Griliches (1961) about the characteristics of the cars in the UK to examine the changes in market prices of different models during the first quarter of 1977 until the fourth quarter of 1991 in a series of cross-section regressions using the method of least squares. A second goal was the use of estimates of the hedonic price model to construct hedonic price indexes for automobiles, which allows to investigate the rising prices of cars due to factors related or not to quality.

Since the work of Griliches (1961) on changes in the quality of cars through the application of hedonic price indexes, several other studies have been developed estimating hedonic prices for durable goods characteristics. However, non-durable goods may also be defined by their characteristics. Depending on the good, the estimated implicit prices provide useful information about consumer preferences, market structure in which the product is sold, price policies, and use of information by industry staff.

Thus, Stanley and Tschirhart (1991) also apply the hedonic technique to estimate the implicit prices of characteristics of morning cereal. The authors chose cereal since it is relatively easy to obtain information on their characteristics in the market, either through experience, advertising or labeling. The results provide information about pricing policies by manufacturers and retailers, additional values that consumers pay for the convenience of cereals, and reaction of consumers in relation to nutrition information contained in the package - the latter being particularly important in the issue of information disclosure.

2.2 Other Applications of the Hedonic Method

In the field of study of public goods, it is cited the work of Brookshire et al. (1982) which measures empirically the value of demand for public goods by presenting a literature review on the use of this technique in public goods. Brookshire et al. (1982) conclude that the hedonic technique is most known and accepted when it assumes that both wages and property values reflect spatial variations in the characteristics of public goods in different communities. Among the public goods and "bads" evaluated by hedonic technique are: the climate, air pollution, social infrastructure, and other community characteristics such as noise level and ethnic composition.

However, Brookshire et al. (1982) propose a technique to obtain information directly from families or individuals about their willingness to pay for public goods in

cases where there are limitations of statistical information. An example would be the situation of a beautiful landscape, valued by a group of agents but threatened by air pollution and possible installation of a coal plant. Even though it is possible to charge more than the value of clean air and the visibility of the landscape that can follow the installation of the plant, information on the value of visibility is needed before construction, so that it is possible to perform a socially optimal decision on the location of a plant and equipment to control pollution. Thus, the hedonic method is not available because the scarcity of local people before the company's establishment makes the use of data on salaries or property value impossible.

In international literature, the hedonic technique is also applied in healthcare goods. For instance, it is cited the work by Cutler et al. (1999) that estimated price indexes for the treatment of heart attacks. This paper presents two alternatives to price indexes: the Index of Prices for Services (SIP), which prices the specific treatments offered, and a Cost of Living Index (COL), which prices results in health of patients in order to determine how much of the improvement in health is the result of medical treatment compared to other factors.

The paper concludes that a price index adjusted for quality of services had increased less than the traditional indices. Thus, according to Cutler et al. (1999), the detailed illustrations of medical price indexes suggest that, at least in the case of heart attacks, medical prices are not increasing much, and may even be declining.

Cutler et al. (1999) observed that the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics has recently improved its measurement of quality in medical care prices. Recently reviewed methods attempt to include quality settings, asking the hospitals to report major changes in the conditions indicated treatments. According to these authors, the rapid advancement in technology and dissemination of medical care require the development of indexes of cost of living as implemented in this work.

In the field of informatics, we highlight the work of Berndt and Rappaport (2001), which examines the stability of hedonic prices parameters of computers over the years 1976-1999, as well as the fairness of the parameters of hedonic prices between desktops and mobile phones. The three characteristics which the authors focus are the hard disk, the processor speed and amount of RAM. It also added other variables, such as the availability of CD-ROM, in addition to the brand. Among the results, it appears that from year 1987 onwards the estimated coefficients differ significantly from models of desktop and mobile phones. Adjusted for changes in quality, prices of PCs have declined dramatically, and those declines accelerated in the 1990s.

2.3 Empirical Works in Brazil

Among empirical works in Brazil, the study by Oliveira (1997) sought to specifically measure the value of air quality related to housing activity. Oliveira (1997) presented a theoretical model that gives basis for the method of hedonic pricing that is not different than that of Rosen's (1974). Thus, using the theoretical model of hedonic prices in the assessment of benefits caused by a possible reduction in air pollution in the region of São Paulo. This empirical study sought to estimate the hedonic function for the housing of São Paulo; estimate the compensated demand functions of the characteristic "air pollution"; and do simulations of gains in consumer surplus related to the improvement in weather conditions in different regions of the city.

The work by Pereira (2004) is also an application of the hedonic price index developed by Lancaster in the restaurants in St. Paul, whose innovation was to consider the public that consumes the restaurant as an attribute of the restaurant. The main objective of Pereira (2004) was to measure the interpersonal influence among university students consumers of restaurants in the city of São Paulo applying the method of hedonic price index. Its secondary purpose was to contribute to the development of a theory that explains how marketing is done to interpersonal influence between consumers. The population sample adopted was the population of students of the main courses of Business and Marketing in the city of São Paulo.

Applied to real estate is the study of Sartoris (1996) whose objective was the estimation of a market model for housing for the city of São Paulo. In particular, the model estimated referred to real estate offerings, or buildings recorded between 1994 and 1995 in São Paulo, in which it was taken into account the characteristics inherent to them for the formation of prices, such as the number of bedrooms, bathrooms, garages, floor area and total area.

The model built by Sartoris (1996) was within a context of market equilibrium, involving the estimation of the equation of supply and demand and focusing on the supply and demand of two features: the floor area and total area of the property. The features included in the model were given, mostly by common sense, considering, among other attributes, the area of the property itself and the area actually built, the quality of construction, characteristics such as number of bedrooms, bathrooms and garages, in addition to income, location and availability of public services.

For services, only the variables related to health and safety factors had significant coefficients, but the coefficient on public health assumed the opposite sign to what was expected, raising the suspicion that it is in fact measuring some other aspect, such as the standard of living that, when high, is associated with a greater presence of private health. The income and population density had significant coefficients and assumed expected signs, positive in both cases, the other variables and components of the vector of characteristics, ie, number of bedrooms, bathrooms, garages, elevators, floors and total area were also significant. Furthermore, the variables representing sewage and slums were insignificant. According to Sartori (1999), no significance is due to the fact that most properties of the sample were located in districts where there was incidence of slums and tenements, as well as households with poor access to sewer.

3. METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

3.1 Research Problem

What are the attributes, both intrinsic and location wise that in fact value and devalue the residential buildings in RMSP?

3.2 Study Hypotheses

In this paper, the hypothesis is that traditional regions of the municipality of São Paulo (the West and Central-South), including the region of Alphaville, are among the most valued in accordance with the hedonic prices approach. Additionally, although it is expected that the Central Zone is among the most valued, the statistical insignificance of

the results is expected given the heterogeneity of this region. For intrinsic attributes, no specific hypothesis has been proposed.

3.3 Objectives

3.3.1 General Objectives

The objective of this study was to develop a model of hedonic prices in order to analyze which attributes value (or devalue) residential buildings in the RMSP.

3.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. Present the theory of hedonic prices
2. Perform technical review of the literature
3. Observe other applications of the hedonic method
4. Analyze empirical Brazilian works which use the hedonic method
5. Observe the uses and limitations of the hedonic price method
6. Apply the hedonic prices model for housing in the RMSP
7. Perform critical appraisal concerning the purpose of each attribute in a study on housing prices in the RMSP

3.4 Method

It is applied the statistical method, since it investigates the quantitative relationship, assuming margin of error, between the effects of changes in housing attributes of the RMSP on their prices, based on data banks and econometrics tools.

3.5 Data Collection

For the application of statistical method and the theory of hedonic prices in the real estate sector of the economy, data has been gathered from EMBRAESP (Brazilian Corporation for Property Studies) for residential offerings in RMSP (Metropolitan Region of São Paulo) from September 1998 to August 2007.

Prices in R\$ (Brazilian Real) have been updated based on INCC (National Index of Construction Cost) of February 2007. This is a continuous statistic series, with monthly frequency, for the 18 municipalities of the following state capitals of Brazil: Aracaju, Belém, Belo Horizonte, Brasília, Campo Grande, Curitiba, Florianópolis, Fortaleza, Goiânia, João Pessoa, Maceió, Manaus, Porto Alegre, Recife, Rio de Janeiro, Salvador, São Paulo and Vitória. The national index has been released by FGV (Fundação Getúlio Vargas) since January 1944.

Thus, properties values recorded throughout different times are in the same standard of analysis, allowing for the application of the hedonic method and proper interpretation on the effects of each attribute available on the price per square meter of floor area of buildings in the RMSP.

3.6 Technical Analysis

By using the attributes available related to the tested buildings, variables have been classified as presented on Table 1.

Table 1 – Definition of the hedonic variables of intrinsic attributes

VARIABLE	VARIABLE DEFINITION
ANDARES	number of floors
AREAUTIL	floor área in M ²
BANH	number of baths
BLOCOS	number of blocks
COBER	number of units at the top of the building
DORM	number of bedrooms
ELEV	number of elevators
GAR	number of garages
UNIDAND	number of units per floor

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on data gathered from EMBRAESP.

Then, in order to examine all types of businesses available (horizontal and vertical), dummies have been created for this attribute, according to Table 2 below.

Table 2 - Definition of Dummy related to business type

VARIABLE	VARIABLE DEFINITION
DUMMY_VERTICAL	Vertical Buildings = 1 Horizontal Buildings = 0

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on data gathered from EMBRAESP.

It was then used the Map of the Sub-Administrations to classify the real estate offerings by region and under official rules in order to properly interpret the dummies in the model for the attribute "location". Aiming to avoid the excess of dummies and make the analysis more effective, we have added up the Northwest and Northeast zones into a single variable, doing the same to the East Zone 1 and Eastern Zone 2 (referred to as "NORTE" and "LESTE", respectively). Thus, dummies for the regions in São Paulo have been created, as presented on Table 3.

Table 3 - Definition of Location Dummies in the Municipality of São Paulo

VARIABLE	VARIABLE DEFINITION
CENTRO	Central Area of São Paulo
CENTROSUL	Center-Southern Zone
LESTE	Eastern Zone
NORTE	Northern Zone
SUDESTE	Southeastern Zone
SUL	Southern Zone

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on data gathered from EMBRAESP.

For metropolitan areas not located in São Paulo in which there were less than 20 observations, data has been grouped into a separate dummy, called RMSPR (Other Regions of RMSP), in order not to exist an excessive number of dummies, favoring the interpretive power of the model to be developed, as shown in Table 4 below. The regions that comprise RMSPR are Arujá, Caieiras, Cajamar, Carapicuíba, Embu, Ferraz

de Vasconcelos, Guararema, Itapevi, Itaquaquecetuba, Jandira, Mariporã, Santana's Parnaíba, Suzano and Vargem Grande Paulista.

Table 4 - Definition of Dummies for Location in the RMSP

VARIABLE	VARIABLE DEFINITION
RMSP1	Alphaville
RMSP2	Cotia
RMSP3	Diadema
RMSP4	Guarulhos
RMSP5	Mauá
RMSP6	Mogi das Cruzes
RMSP7	Osasco
RMSP8	Santo André
RMSP9	São Bernardo do Campo
RMSP10	São Caetano do Sul
RMSP11	Taboão da Serra
RMSPR	Other Regions of RMSP

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on data gathered from EMBRAESP.

Then, from the cross-section database, a multiple regression of ordinary least squares (MQO) has been performed, in which the price (in R\$) per M^2 of real estate offerings is the dependent variable and the attributes of residential releases are the exogenous variables. The obtained results show which attributes in fact value and devalue the residential buildings of RMSP and what the possible reasons for the trends are.

Finally, in section destined to the final remarks, a critical appreciation in relation to the results produced by hedonic prices regression has been developed, returning to the theme comprehending which attributes from the sample data value and devalue the homes of RMSP, whose information can contribute to more effective measures for the construction of buildings that can be applied both to RMSP as well as to Brazil if verified trends are assumed national. Thus, the results provide enlightening information on marginal prices that are useful in both private and public valuations in Brazil.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The Data

Initially, multiple scatter graphs have been elaborated to observe how each exogenous variable reacts against the dependent variable price per M^2 of floor area, called *PRECOUTIL_INCC*. In an initial analysis, it is observed from Figure 1 that the intrinsic attributes with the greatest apparent potential to enhance a property value is the number of bedrooms, bathrooms, garages and floor area. Furthermore, the least apparent potential is the number of elevators, units at the top of the building and blocks. Finally, the seemingly ambiguous relationships are the number of units per floor and floors.

Additionally, it is presented the average M^2 prices of residential property for each region of the RMSP. From Figure 2, we have found that regions with the highest value are the Center-Southern Zone, Western Zone and Central Zone of São Paulo. Moreover, the least valued regions are Taboão da Serra, Other Regions of RMSP,

Diadema and Mauá. However, the econometric results allow for a more precise data analysis in this study.

Figure 1 - Multiple scatter graphs of exogenous variables against the dependent variable.

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on data gathered from EMBRAESP.

Figure 2 – Bar graph for RMSP areas and their average M² price
 Source: Elaborated by the authors based on data gathered from EMBRAESP.

4.2 The Hedonic Price Model

In order to examine more precisely the relationship between the price of M² of each property and its attributes under study, we proceed with the econometric analysis of data by developing the hedonic price model presented on Table 1.

According to the F test of multiple regression, no problems of multicollinearity in the model is evidenced, and the R^2 component indicates that 44,02% of the model can be explained by their independent variables included in the various attributes of a property. This result is expected and represents a good level of explanatory power. This is because, as the model expresses, about 56% of the property is not explained by its intrinsic attributes and location, but by external factors such as services related to health, safety and education (SARTORIS, 1996).

For the statistical diagnosis of normality and residual heteroskedasticity, since the sample size under study is large (4774 observations), we resort to the asymptotic properties of estimators, which ensures that the estimators of this hedonic prices model are not biased.

Table 1 - Results of the Hedonic Price Model

N. of Obs =	4774		
F(27, 4746)	133.26		
Prob > F	***		
R ²	0.4402		
PRECOUTIL_INCC	Coeff.	Std. Deviation	t
DORM	-222.5311	16.9251	-13.15 ***
BANH	24.9053	20.7801	1.20
GAR	275.7579	16.9686	16.25 ***
ELEV	-11.2394	3.3783	-3.33 ***
COBER	5.8201	4.4305	1.31
BLOCOS	-5.1197	4.4216	-1.16
UNIDAND	37.4958	3.8982	9.62 ***
ANDARES	22.6262	1.8743	12.07 ***
AREAUTIL	2.3721	0.1976	12.01 ***
DUMMY_VERTICAL	-182.3353	34.3407	-5.31 ***
CENTRO	17.6033	52.7878	0.33
CENTROSUL	85.7666	29.6448	2.89 ***
LESTE	-226.5347	35.2059	-6.43 ***
NORTE	-245.7703	31.9589	-7.69 ***
SUDESTE	-246.2641	31.2450	-7.88 ***
SUL	-103.5005	29.5527	-3.50 ***
RMSP1	-188.2597	84.6863	-2.22 **
RMSP2	-230.6257	73.3884	-3.14 ***
RMSP3	-371.6676	114.1364	-3.26 ***
RMSP4	-309.6650	56.2521	-5.50 ***
RMSP5	-344.3036	123.5856	-2.79 ***
RMSP6	-175.7825	123.4955	-1.42
RMSP7	-287.1017	82.3753	-3.49 ***
RMSP8	-406.8666	45.9239	-8.86 ***
RMSP9	-249.8104	43.4431	-5.75 ***
RMSP10	-258.2940	61.2746	-4.22 ***
RMSP11	-341.8258	114.0198	-3.00 ***
RMSPR	-285.0274	80.1404	-3.56 ***
C	735.4887	43.9744	16.73 ***

Source: Results obtained through software STATA 10.0 from EMBRAESP collected data for the proposed model of hedonic prices.

Note: *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, * significant at 10%.

4.2.1 Analysis of the Intrinsic Attributes of the Hedonic Variables

Regarding the variable related to the number of bedrooms, it is observed that its coefficient is negative and highly significant to the model, indicating that additional bedrooms may adversely affect the price of a property. At first glance, the coefficient's sign appears to be against common sense. Naturally, the number of rooms is a variable that defines the target audience to be reached. Although buildings with a different amount of rooms are of the highest potential for valuation in the market (see Figure 1), it appears that, *ceteris paribus*, additional bedrooms depreciate the price of a property, since the area per capita is more important than the number of bedrooms itself. Thus, a property of only 1 bedroom can have as much or more value than another of 3 bedrooms

that do not offer the same comfort in terms of space and luxury attributes (such as a suite) in relation to the first.

Analyzing the variable related to the number of bathrooms, there is a coefficient that is positive, not reaching the 10% significance in the model. It is interpreted that, within a building, individuals or groups of individuals value their own bathroom/suites. Thus, separate bathrooms exist for different family members as well as for guests and employees. Moreover, by non-significance of the statistical parameter, it appears that the number of bathrooms is not a crucial variable to add value to property, suggesting the existence of further relevant variables. The very nature of a bathroom - its area and the presence of certain attributes such as bathtub and hydro - are potentially more important than quantity itself to add value to property.

It appears that the parameter related to the number of vacancies in the garage is the highest among the attributes in question, being highly significant as expected. It is empirically evidenced that it is a characteristic of high perceived value and, given the increasing number of vehicles per capita both in the RMSP and in major Brazilian cities, the quantity is an attribute itself and directly related to real estate appraisal.

From the negative and highly significant coefficient given by the variable related to the number of elevators, it is interpreted that additional elevators do not increase the value of the property. Thus, adding elevators to the building is not an effective way to enhance property value. Similarly, observing the variable related to the number of units at the top of the building, even though its coefficient assumes positive value, it is not significant at 10%. Thus, evidence does not present a satisfactory reliability in relation to the number of units at the top of a building and its capacity to increase the respective apartments' values.

Analyzing the variable representing the number of blocks, there is a negative factor that is not statistically significant at 10%. Thus, additional blocks in a condominium may have a depressive effect on the value of the property, possibly related to loss of privacy and exclusivity perceived by the consumer, which can also be interpreted that consumers do not perceive added value in condominiums with several blocks. However, no confidence is evidenced that additional blocks in a condo depreciates the value of a property. In fact, several real estate offerings are composed by blocks with attributes such as a differentiated structure of both leisure and security.

For the parameter related to units per floor, it is observed that the coefficient is positive and highly significant to the model. Units per floor is a valuable attribute, since it represents the possibility of division of the condominium taxes. Additionally, a structure of courts, pool, gym, is generally associated with a greater supply of apartments within a building, so that the actual number of properties sold covers the building costs as quickly as possible. Thus, the logic of building tax division among the owners is valid to interpret this attribute and its respective coefficient.

The coefficient of the variable related to the number of floors is positive and highly significant to the model, being one attribute that assesses the value of a property. This phenomenon may be related to the fact that apartments established in upper floors are less affected by negative externalities such as street noises and sometimes enjoy a more privileged view. Additionally, buildings with a number of floors above the average also relate to the supply of a condominium with differentiated structure, offering greater security and attributes, affecting positively even the lower building floors.

Analyzing the parameter related to floor area, the coefficient is positive and highly significant as expected. It is considered the "attribute of attributes" for the value increase of a residential property. *A priori*, it is valued more spacious rooms, since it is an attribute more directly related to the comfort than the number of rooms themselves. However, given the rising costs of square meter both in RMSP as well as in other major cities in the world, the lower floor area of a building pays off with common areas usually provided with design and luxury, and more technology in security, in order to add value to property, which enables the understanding of the positive coefficient with significantly lower value relative to other factors of intrinsic attributes that increase property value.

4.2.2 Business Type Dummy Analysis

Analyzing the dummy related to the type of venture, it is observed that the horizontalisation is more valued than vertical housing. Since the decision to buy a property is the analysis of several attributes that make up a good, even with the growing concern of the inhabitants of the RMSP with regard to security, the attribute "horizontal" remains valuable despite being opposed by other negative attributes (such as the security implicit in the attributes related to location), which makes it rewarding to choose a horizontal property.

4.2.3 Location Dummy Analysis

In order to analyze the dummies related to the attribute "location", we highlight that the analyzed coefficients are have the Western Zone as a reference because it is the zone of greatest number of observations in the database. Thus, unlike the intrinsic attributes of variables, the dummies are not analyzed according to the sign of their coefficients, but by their relative values to other regions.

From the results of the regression, it appears that the Central Zone is the second most valued of RMSP region, but its coefficient is not statistically significant at 10%, which represents the intrinsic heterogeneity of this region. This result was expected, since, although there exist both valued and decaying neighborhoods, proximity to many shops, and centers of health, education and culture of excellence, means that this region is among the most valued of RMSP to dwell due to its high relative convenience.

Observing the dummy related to the Center-Southern Zone and the highly significant coefficient, this region is the most valued in RMSP. This is an area that enjoys the convenience of a central region, harboring the first segment of Paulista Avenue – the most important address in the city and financial center of the state and country - the Ibirapuera Park and Botanic Garden, not suffering the negative externalities from crowding and saturation of the Central Zone. Neighborhoods such as Moema, with a large real estate speculation, Vila Nova Conceição, with the most expensive square meter in the Municipality according to Coelho da Fonseca Real Estate Company, and traditional neighborhoods such as Vila Mariana and Higienópolis.

Analyzing the dummy representing the West Zone, it is among the most valued of RMSP, which is just behind the central regions and Central and South. With the center-south zone, it forms the "Southwest vector" which is the main axis of development in the city. Following the Central Zone, it is the region with the greatest amount of historical properties registered by Condephaat (Council for Protection of

Cultural, Archaeological and Artistic Patrimony), some even forming entire neighborhoods as the City Lapa. It is also the local concentration of the cultural life of the city, with numerous cultural establishments and also two major universities in the city: the USP and PUC-SP. This is also the region with intense high standard residential speculation, although much of the region has already been consolidated since the mid-twentieth century.

Regarding the dummy related to the Eastern Zone, it is not among the most valued in São Paulo Municipality, behind the Central regions, Center-Southern, Western and Southern Zone of the Capital, occupying a previous place the aspect of recovery. It is the most populated region in São Paulo, essentially formed by commercial establishments and popular housing and is generally regarded as a "dorm-region" of the city. The average income of the population is below average for the city and the rate of unemployment and crime is high. Thus, the results obtained are consistent with the expected results in this study of real estate offerings.

Analyzing the dummy of the Northern Zone, it is not among the most valued in the Municipality of São Paulo, ranked before the least valued zone. Having been the last region of the city to be colonized, its development is very recent. Its history of colonization started with the exploration of the regions of Campinas and Jundiaí, where it is located the Anhanguera Highway which gives access to these cities. The North Eastern is the only city not to be served by Metropolitan Trains Company (CPTM), and the Northwestern region is crossed by Line A of CPTM and is not served by subway. It is formed by a population of low purchasing power in general, although it hosts some high standard residential in the districts of Santo Domingos and Pirituba. Thus, the results obtained are consistent with the results expected for this region.

For the dummy representing the Southeastern Zone, by analyzing its coefficient, is in last place under the aspect of valuation in São Paulo Municipality. Although much of its population belongs to middle-class, it is one of the most heterogeneous in the city, while hosting the district of Heliópolis (formerly considered the largest slum in Brazil) and some of the richest neighborhoods of São Paulo as Tatuapé and Garden Anália Franco. Moreover, the average of the data sample for the price per square meter (see Figure 2), which indicated the Southeast Zone as one of the two least developed in the city, it could not be expected that this region reached a high relative coefficient.

Observing the coefficient of the dummy related to the South Zone, it appears that it is in an intermediate position among São Paulo regions, which is ranked behind the Center-Southern Zone, Central and Western Zone. As the region's largest city, despite being characterized as a needy area with a relatively high crime rate per capita in the city of São Paulo, "islands" of wealth exist in the region, especially in the district of Capela do Socorro, near the district of Santo Amaro, located in the Center-Southern Zone. Thus, the coefficient captures such value for residential entries that was originally in the study of average price per square meter (see Figure 2), in which the region is also in an intermediate position.

For dummies related to the metropolitan areas of Greater São Paulo, it is observed that the most valued regions according to data analyzed by the hedonic prices method are, in descending order, Mogi das Cruzes (a statistically insignificant 10%), Alphaville, Cotia, São Bernardo do Campo, São Caetano do Sul State, Other Regions of RMSP, Osasco, Guarulhos, the Taboão Serra, Mauá, Diadema, and Santo André.

Thus, the results evidence its consistency as it presents the high relative value of Alphaville, region of residence of a significant portion of the elite of the city, São

Bernardo do Campo, with its economy based originally in the automobile industry but which have great importance to the diversification growing service sector in the city, and São Caetano do Sul, which has the best social indicators across the country and is considered an exemplary city in many aspects of the HDI (Human Development Index) released by the United Nations.

5. CONCLUSION

It is considered that entrepreneurship is a set of behaviors that promote the ability to manage and exploit opportunities, improve business processes and invent. However, the entrepreneurial activity often does not often apply tools and techniques available for the identification of relevant attributes to the proceedings and appropriate analysis of the strategy to be adopted in the opening and improvement of a business.

In the dynamic attributes of the competition, it is observed the continuous production of new attributes in products. If a good obtains success, the other competitors will supply it in a chain process. This fact emphasizes the importance of maintaining the leadership to introduce new attributes or to produce new goods or services that directly meet consumers' needs. Attributes of success creates competitive advantage for the company, leading to abnormal returns and market share increase.

This paper aims to present the hedonic prices technique for entrepreneurship assessment of products, services and location aspects for the opening and improvement of processes in a business. Sometimes the intuition or questionnaire may not adequately capture the behavior of the consumer itself, and the tool of hedonic prices may be a more direct approach to the empirical verification of attributes that are relevant to the business, be it intrinsic or extrinsic to the same.

Thus, it is useful to apply the hedonic pricing approach, given that the differentiation occurs both through the enhancement of valuable attributes and the creation of new products and services that offer more directly the attributes from which consumers perceive value, favoring a strategy for better positioning in relation to intuitive processes, client research, or dialectical (march in the opposite direction to the crowd).

Even if some attribute is not offered to the market in a direct manner, it is possible to obtain proxies for the identification of attributes that can have great degree of acceptability in the market, even if consumers do not realize *a priori* that they are valuing a specific attribute. In a strategic focus, it may constitute a tool for entrepreneurial perception of an apparent causal ambiguity between the use of resources and generation of competitive advantage in supplying a product or service.

Applying the tool of hedonic prices in the real estate sector of RMSP, we verify which attributes provide perceived consumer value and the role of location in favoring the establishment of new ventures. Similarly, you can use this tool in a variety of segments for its flexibility in the inclusion of tangible and intangible attributes.

The hedonic pricing approach can serve as a proxy for the focused entrepreneur behavior on his strategy in the establishment and improvement of business, avoiding the purely ceremonial application of business models and supply of products and services with certain characteristics that do not involve abnormal returns.

Fulfilling the objective of this paper, we have analyzed what elements value and devalue the homes in RMSP, whose information contributes to more effective measures

in business valuation in both private and public real estate as well as in other segments in the identification of attributes that are valued and devalued by consumers.

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